

Detection of Unknown Defects in CFRP Using Eddy Current Pulsed Thermography and Microwave NDT

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Abstract

Detection of defects in carbon fiber reinforced composite (CFRP) materials with complex geometry has been a challenging task for aerospace industries. Driven by the Student Challenge of NDT-Aerospace 2019, this paper aims to detect and characterize a contaminated bonding and five inclusions with unknown positions in a CFRP specimen by using both eddy current pulsed thermography (ECPT) and microwave NDT. The results from the employed techniques are evaluated and compared in terms of signal to noise ratio and probability of detection. Results show that it is difficult for microwave NDT to identify the man-made debonding or inclusions. For ECPT, one contaminated bonding and four out of five inclusions can be detected with high SNR values.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) materials are widely used in many industrial applications, e.g., aerospace, automobile, civil infrastructure, with their excellent mechanical properties and superb resistance to thermal-chemical corrosion and abrasion [1-3]. Defects, such as inclusions, debonding, porosity, impact damages, delamination, may occur in the manufacturing stage or during the service life. Inclusions or debonding between the layers of CFRP might weaken the mechanical properties of the composites, which leads to the potential risk of functional failure [4]. Up to now, many nondestructive testing and evaluation (NDT&E) techniques, such as ultrasonic, eddy current, active thermography, have been widely utilized to detect and quantify the delamination in CFRP [5-7]. Active thermography is one promising NDT&E method for testing and evaluating CFRP materials within its advantages of fast testing speed, large detecting area and quantitative analysis [8, 9]. As a promising candidate, eddy current pulsed thermography (ECPT), a.k.a. induction thermography or electromagnetic thermography, takes the advantages of the infrared imaging (with high a resolution and sensitivity) as well as the active-electromagnetic heat excitation. These advantages enable ECPT to easily heat conductive materials or further

characterize their geometric parameters [10-13]. Microwave NDT is another promising technique for CFRP testing [14, 15] with the potential of in-situ deployment. The defect detection in CFRP with complex geometry has been a challenge for aerospace industries since the thermal response (in ECPT testing) and the electromagnetic response (in microwave NDT) highly depend on the curved surfaces. This paper investigates the capabilities of both ECPT and microwave NDT to detect unknown contaminated bonding and inclusions in a dedicated CFRP specimen. The rest of this paper is structured as: the fundamentals of ECPT and microwave NDT and the study diagram are introduced in Section 2; Section 3 presents the experimental studies; further, Section 4 briefly discusses the findings from the experimental results; the conclusion and future work are given in Section 5.

2. Theoretical background and study diagram

2.1. Fundamentals of ECPT

In 3D Cartesian coordinate, the heat diffusion equation with an electromagnetic heating source is:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \lambda \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \right) = J \cdot E \quad (1)$$

where, ρ , C_p , and λ are the material density, the specific heat and the thermal conductivity, respectively. J and E are the current density and electric field, respectively.

By using ECPT technique, either ohmic heating or heat diffusion can contribute the defect detection. For the thin shell structure of CFRP materials, the ohmic heating is volumetric heating, which takes place together with heat diffusion. In this study, kernel principal component analysis (KPCA)-based features extracted from the thermal response are used to detect the unknown defects in a CFRP specimen. A detailed description of KPCA-based ECPT testing for the delamination depth evaluation can be found [16].

2.2. Fundamentals of MOEWI

Microwave NDT of a CFRP specimen can be performed by an open-ended waveguide (OEW) probe antenna

mounted on an XY scanner. The OEW is excited by a vector network analyzer (VNA) and thus the reflection coefficients (S_{11} or Γ) within the OEW bandwidth can be obtained in the dominant TE_{10} mode at every scanning point. The reflection coefficient at the aperture of the waveguide will be related to the coupling between the OEW termination impedance and the specimen, which also includes the impedance of air due to the lift-off (distance between the OEW and the specimen). Based on the transmission line theory, the reflection coefficient at the waveguide aperture can be calculated as follows:

$$\Gamma = \frac{Z_{in} - Z_{WG}}{Z_{in} + Z_{WG}} \quad (2)$$

where Γ is the reflection coefficient at the aperture of OEW. Z_{WG} is the waveguide termination impedance and Z_{in} is the intrinsic impedance, which is expressed as:

$$Z_{in} = \sqrt{\frac{j\omega\mu}{\sigma + j\omega\epsilon}} \quad (3)$$

where, μ , σ , ϵ , are the permeability, conductivity and permittivity of the specimen, respectively.

A CFRP composite specimen is a complex mixture of conductive and non-conductive materials, i.e. carbon fiber and polymer matrix. Therefore, there are influences from different material properties to the measurement of reflection coefficient of each scanning position. Another influence may come the lift-off variation due to the geometrical complexity of the specimen. For feature extraction of wideband reflection coefficient data, KPCA can be used for separating defects and the CFRP texture. In addition, KPCA can also be used for reducing the lift-off effects caused by a curved GFRP specimen.

2.3. Study diagram

The study diagram for defects detection is shown in Fig. 1. It is started by configuring the parameters of the ECPT and microwave NDT setup. Then possible defective areas (ROIs) are selected based on the result of optical thermography (see Figs. 2(b) and (d)). Further, KPCA are used for defect detection. Then, the results from ECPT

Fig. 2. Test specimen. (a) and (c) are photos of specimen taken from the top and side, respectively. (b) and (d) show the initial results of OT from the two corresponding views, respectively.

and microwave NDT are compared by signal to noise ratio (SNR) or probability of detection (POD).

3. Experimental studies

In this section, the experimental studies are conducted to investigate the KPCA-based results from both ECPT and microwave NDT.

3.1. CFRP specimen with unknown defects

Figs. 2(a) and (c) show the specimen used in experimental studies. This specimen was made of CFRP fabric material by prepreg method. In the manufacturing process, this specimen was manually introduced a contaminated bonding in the T-profile and five inclusions (foreign objects) with unknown positions. The minimum inclusion size is 3×3 mm. Prior to conducting the ECPT and microwave NDT, a quick inspection was deployed using optical thermography (OT). Fig. 2(b) and (d) show the results from OT, which are used to initially locate five possible defective areas or ROIs for further testing.

3.2. ECPT configuration

Fig. 3 shows the layout of the ECPT configuration used for experimental studies. It contains four units, an excitation module with a rectangle coil, an infrared camera, a signal generator, and a computer. In this study, only the operational RMS current and frequency of the excitation module were changed to 350 A and 274 kHz, respectively. A 10 mm lift-off between the coil's bottom edge and the top faces of the specimen was kept in all the ROIs' testing.

Fig. 1. Study diagram.

Fig. 2. Test specimen. (a) and (c) are photos of specimen taken from the top and side, respectively. (b) and (d) show the initial results of OT from the two corresponding views, respectively.

Fig. 3. ECPT configuration.

Fig. 4. Microwave NDT configuration.

3.3. Microwave NDT configuration

Fig. 4 shows the layout of the microwave NDT configuration used for experimental studies. It mainly contains a vector network analyzer (VNA), a computer, an open-ended waveguide probe, and an X-Y scanner. The X-Y scanner is controlled by a computer through the XY-scanner controller with the scanning step size at 0.5 mm for both x and y directions. The WR-42 OEW with 18-26.5 GHz bandwidth (K-band) was used in the experiment. The reflection coefficient (S_{11}) of each scanning position from the VNA is recorded by the computer. Due to the geometrical complexity of the specimen, the experiment.

3.4. Feature extraction and comparison

By using KPCA method, Fig. 5 shows the results of ECPT testing. All the five possible defects (four inclusions and one contaminated bonding) can be clearly identified. It shows that the shape of D_1 and D_5 is a parallelogram. The shape of D_2 is a small rectangle in the middle of the bonding area. D_3 is a strip at the edge. And D_4 has a trapezoid shape. Additionally, Table 1 provides the estimated area and the SNR of each possible defect.

Table 1 Estimated areas and SNR of defects

defect	area (pixels)	SNR
D_1	4315 (360)*	1.32
D_2	3876 (160)*	1.65
D_3	3320 (80)*	1.83
D_4	4818 (430)*	1.12
D_5	5106 (500)*	1.85

*: the ground truth values (mm^2) are roughly measured from calibrated OT data and shown in the parentheses. The shape of D_1 , D_2 , D_3 , and D_5 is a parallelogram. D_4 has a trapezoid shape.

Fig. 6 depicts the Microwave NDT results using KPCA based feature extraction. Note that only the results of D_1 and D_2 are presented. Fig 6(a) shows the microwave NDT results with $\sim 5\text{mm}$ lift-off for a region covering D_1 and D_2 . It can be seen that PC3 shows a contrast (dark) area at the same location as the defect D_2 , while PC6 presents a contrast area at the location of the contaminated bonding defect D_1 . To further investigate the location of D_2 , the scan area of microwave NDT is reduced to cover only D_2 . With a smaller scan area, the lift-off can be reduced to $\sim 2\text{mm}$ because the specimen curve within this area is not as significant as the area covering D_1 and D_2 . Fig 6(b) exhibits the results with $\sim 2\text{mm}$ lift-off for the region covering the contaminated bonding defect D_2 . In these results, PC3 shows a long dark area which is likely caused by the contaminated defect D_2 . Additionally, with the lower lift-off measurement, the fiber texture are seen in PC5, PC6 and PC10. However, the SNR of the two possible areas are below 1.

4. Discussion

The above experimental results show that:

(1) In ECPT testing, the only one contaminated bonding can be easily detected since the size of the contaminated area is relatively large, which can slow down the heat dissipation and contribute to an abnormal heat distribution. For the five inclusions, ECPT can detect four of them. However, from Fig 5(e), we might find that the missed one locates near the right side of D_3 . Limited by the resolution of IR camera, this result is not clear. From Table 1, the relation between the estimated area (from KPCA results) and the measured ground truth values can be obtained, and the POD curve from six repeated testing data is shown in Fig. 7.

(2) Overall, detection results using the microwave NDT and PCA feature extraction are encouraging since some defect areas, at least D_1 and D_2 , are visible. However, the defect detections are less convincing as compared to those from ECPT. Unlike the ECPT results, the defect areas come with arbitrary shapes and incomparable to the more regular defect shapes obtained from ECPT. The strength of microwave NDT is that it can bring multiple physical influences from the measurement, such as specimen contour, fiber pattern, and the defects. These multiple physical parameters, however, cause detection of defects becomes challenging. In addition, the low penetration depth of microwave limits the detection of defects because they are located underneath the front fiber layer. Furthermore, the geometrical complexity of the CFRP specimen makes the lift off must be sufficiently high to cover the curved surface. The lift-off, although small, may cause larger multiple variations in the scattering parameters dataset, thus make feature extractions ineffective to recognize the defects.

Fig. 5. ECPT results of five possible defective areas. (a) Possible defect D₁. (b) Possible defect D₂. (c) Possible defect D₃. (d) Possible defect D₄. (e) Possible defect D₅.

Fig. 6. Microwave NDT results of two possible defective areas. (a) Possible defect D₁ and D₂ with measurement at ~5 mm lift-off (b) Possible defect D₂ with measurement at ~2 mm lift-off.

Fig. 7. POD curve from ECPT result.

5. Conclusions

This paper investigates the capabilities of both ECPT and microwave NDT for detecting unknown defects in the thin shell structure of CFRP. The features used for comparison are based on KPCA method. Results show that although microwave NDT can detect impact damages in CFRP materials [17], it is difficult for microwave NDT to identify the man-made debonding or inclusions. For ECPT, one contaminated bonding and four out of five inclusions can be detected with high SNR values.

Further work will investigate the electromagnetic response of different frequency bands in microwave NDT and focus on the optimization of coil design to reduce the influence of curved surfaces.

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